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Abstract

The main goal of the article is to focus on the problem of socio-philosophical reflection in the context of modern innovations, given their importance in the process of cognition. Reflection, on the one hand, is the process of processing the knowledge gained, and on the other hand, this is a separate activity on the formation of new knowledge in the field of thinking. To achieve post-non-classical social reflection, it is necessary to analyze and update the socio-philosophical aspect of the new notions of scientific knowledge used. From this point of view, it is wise to begin with the concepts of complexity and chaos.

Keywords: reflection, social cognition, society, post-neoclassicism, complexity, chaos, nonlinear thinking.

Introduction. The problem of social reflection is of great importance in terms of establishing optimal tactics and strategies for the cultural development of society in the context of scientific innovations. Socio-philosophical reflection is a process of processing acquired knowledge and at the same time a line of activity that ensures the discovery of new knowledge in mental activity. The multitude of problems faced by humanity in the modern era forces modern man to increase the potential of his understanding and creativity. By modern era we mean the post-neoclassical stage in the development of science.

The main aim of the article is to focus on the problem of socio-philosophical reflection in the context of modern innovations, given their importance in the process of cognition.

Main matters. For the effectiveness of social reflection, first of all, new concepts that form the basis of the paradigm of post-neoclassical scientific knowledge must be analyzed and reinterpreted from the point of view of social philosophy. Conducting an axiological analysis of the main ideas reflecting the core of empirical material related to the problem of reflection is a very difficult task. Since the 70s of the last century, great strides have been made in understanding the problems of reflection related to such fundamental sciences as chemistry, physics, mathematics and biology. In the social sciences, the use of the category of reflection in research differs from their use in these sciences and is somewhat unconventional. Although this term was first used by the English philosopher J. Locke, in the social and humanitarian fields, it has become relevant only since the end of the 20th century. Today, it can be argued that the scope of this term has expanded significantly, and serious successes have been achieved in understanding the role of reflection in many social studies.

The word "reflection" has many meanings, dictionaries give its various interpretations, including, for example, such meanings as "original meaning", "inner illumination", "return". This is the most important principle of independent thinking, the first step on the path of understanding and comprehension, as well as a necessary component of self-awareness and the process of critical analysis of the content of cognition. Russian

scientist V. S. Shvyrev notes that at a certain stage of the formation and development of scientific knowledge, further progress is impossible without reflection. It is through reflection that the research ability to systematize ideas about the nature of science, its limits and the foundations of research is realized. [1, p. 25]. V. A. Lektorsky considers the increasing role of reflection in the process of cognition as an expression of the process of humanization of modern science [2, p. 37].

Another important aspect of philosophical reflection is its focus on the structures that form the basis of mental activity, the basis of its "fundamental limits". Let us turn to the judgment of the Russian scientist E. G. Yudin. He writes that "philosophical reflection is the self-awareness of mental activity in general, and not of its specific type; so to speak, it is the methodology of any cognition - scientific or unscientific. Its uniqueness is determined by the originality of the philosophical subject, i.e. the search for its fundamental limits. That is, philosophical reflection is the search for logical and other (spiritual, value, emotional, etc.) foundations, as well as forms of spiritual life and culture in general" [3. P. 46].

Nowadays, in social epistemology, as well as in the process of scientific cognition in general, researchers are looking for a solution to the problem of reflection through the widespread use of interdisciplinary paradigms and methodologies based on the foundation of post-neoclassical science. We believe that the first thing to do in this direction is to analyze post—neoclassical ideas about self-developing systems of various social associations and society as a whole. This will undoubtedly be of great benefit for the study of management issues that currently have great practical applications, as well as arousing increasing theoretical interest.

But what should be the social reflection in the context of innovation? What are the problems here? In order to find answers to such questions, let's try to outline possible features of the formation of philosophical reflection of post-neoclassical science in social cognition.

At the present stage of cognition, it is almost impossible to achieve a solution to the problem of socio-philosophical reflection without conducting it through the socio-cognitive filter of post-neoclassical concepts

of complexity, order and chaos. The concept of complexity is the most important concept of synergetics, and therefore it seems appropriate to start considering the features of post-neoclassical philosophical reflection from its analysis.

At the initial stage, it is necessary to systematically consider words and phrases that are close or synonymous with the concept of complexity, as well as all possible concepts that are antonyms and opposites of this concept. In the study of this problem, it is impossible not to mention the names of Belgian scientists G. Nikolis and I. Prigozhin, who were the first to try to explore and understand the nature of the phenomenon of complexity. In a jointly written book, *Cognition of the Complex*, they tried to comprehensively and systematically investigate the features and behavior of complex systems. From the point of view of researchers, the state of "disequilibrium" can be considered as a complex behavior, regardless of whether it is about molecules, biological or social systems. "Complexity in modern cognition refers to the occurrence of bifurcation transitions far from equilibrium and symmetry breaking in the presence of corresponding nonlinearity" [4, p.42]. Nonlinearity is a fundamental property of open systems that ensures a continuous choice of alternatives in its development.

Azerbaijani philosopher A.F. Abbasov identifies a number of basic provisions for the analysis of methodological features that modern researchers will face. These provisions clearly and concisely reflect such issues as the complexity of the characteristics of research objects, trends and mechanisms of their change, the general criterion of synergetic transition, the main parameter regulating the dynamics of activity, how the system determines its fate and in what environment they occur. These individual aspects of understanding complexity in a synergetic sense can be considered a methodological basis that makes it possible to conduct analyses at specific levels by organizing the system. According to A.F. Abbasov, elements of critical-synergetic thinking play a leading role in the creation of non-traditional methodologies [5].

Another Azerbaijani philosopher F. M. Gurbanov notes that in modern science, complexity should be understood in two senses. Firstly, as a quality objectively inherent in systems, and secondly, as a cognitive situation that arises in the process of understanding as a result of human cognitive activity. In both cases, complexity has the qualities of non-linearity, structural and functional improvement, complication of system dynamics, increased uncertainty compared to the previous situation, etc. [6].

In complex systems, the concept of fractality, meaning that newly created structures carry repetitive characteristics at one stage or another of the evolution of the system, reflects the presence of multilevel relationships in complex systems. Therefore, it is believed that knowing the progress on a small scale, it is possible to determine the nature of the processes taking place on a large scale. Or, events occurring in the system are reflected in its subsystems at the local level. The essence and form of manifestation of a complex whole are similar to the essence and forms of manifestation of its

parts, and the factor ensuring the integrity of the system is not a simple algebraic sum of parts, but their functional relationship. This indicates that it is possible to understand complexity even in a chaotic state of the system. If we look at the post-neoclassical scientific paradigm, which continues from the 70s of the 20th century to the present day, we can conclude that the concept of complexity should be involved in scientific reflection, along with the concept of chaos. Getting acquainted with modern theories of complexity, we can conclude that there is a state of complexity called chaos. Chaos theory studies the dependence of all dynamical systems, mathematical, physical, economic or biological, on initial conditions. For some, chaos is just turbulence, for others it is a destructive branch of evolution. Later, those who considered chaos as a set of probabilities began to make up the majority [7, p.72]. In a synergetic sense, chaos has its own structure and represents a more complex and "unaccounted" form of order. This refutes the idea that chaos is the opposite of order. Speaking about the term chaos, first of all it should be pointed out that situations "we call chaotic primarily because we cannot explain them by the logical means of classical science" [8, p.25].

The process of system evolution is characterized by an alternation of relatively stable states. One point should be particularly noted. In a synergetic sense, the very concepts of order and chaos are relative in terms of the scale of observations. What appears to be chaos at the macro level may have an ordered structure at the micro level. For this reason, an exhaustive description of the hierarchical system in synergetics consists of communication between observers of different levels [9, p. 43].

According to Luhmann, social chaos serves as a source of social order for society. Chaos is a source of order in the sense that it stimulates the formation of mechanisms capable of preventing destruction within the system [10, p.203]. It is not trivial to catch an element of randomness in the behavior of individuals, or a group of individuals forming a society. Social chaos refers to dynamics occurring outside of the deterministic rules that man has defined for the system in each historical period. However, it would be wrong to accept this idea in an absolute sense at the level of a post-neoclassical approach. Because chaos and order are inseparable aspects of form. They complement each other, and one can turn into another. That is, we cannot talk about universal chaos or universal order.

Conclusions. As can be seen, in the modern scientific environment, the ability to reflect has become a practical requirement for every serious and independent-minded researcher. This approach allows us to look at the evolution of society as a whole in a completely different aspect. Undoubtedly, scientists are trying to master not only scientific results, but also their reflexive power. That is, the role of personal ability to reflect is very important in the purpose and motivation of the researcher. One of the most characteristic features of modern science is that its evolution is impossible without philosophical reflection.

References

1. Швырев В. С. Научное познание как деятельность. — М., 1994. с. 25-26.
2. Лекторский В. А. Теория познания и современная наука // Философия и социология науки и техники: Ежегодник 1983.— М., 1985 с. 37.
3. Юдин Э. Г. Отношение философии и науки как методологическая проблема// Философия в современном мире. Философия и наука. М., 1972.
4. Николис Г., Пригожий И. Познание сложного. Введение. М., 1990
5. Abbasov Ə.F. Əliyev E. «Sosial idrak fiziki ideyaların təsiri altında» // Müasir mərhələdə sosiomanitar elmlərin sosioloji və metodoloji problemləri, Bakı, 2000, s.
6. Qurbanov F.M.Yeni idraki paradıqmalar və fənlərarası yanaşma. Bakı, “Təknur”, 2015. 352s. səh 29, 7-38
7. Ладенко И. С. Модели рефлексии. — Новосибирск.: Изд-во «Институт философии и права СО РАН», 1992. — 80 с.
8. Митрофанов Б. С. Гносеологический анализ проблемы предмета науки: Дис. ... канд. филос. наук. — Томск, 1980.
9. Розова С. С. Классификационная проблема в современной науке. — Новосибирск, 1986.
10. Луман Н. Общество общества М.: Логос, 2004. 231 с.